

IT SPECIALISTS AS CATALYSTS FOR UZBEKISTAN'S DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Askarov Farhod Raxmatovich,

FerPI, Economics department assistant.

Mahammadjonova Gulbahor Shavkatjon qizi,

FerPI, Economics department, 3 grade student

Mo'sinov Jamshidbek A'zamjon o'g'li,

FerPI, Economics department, 3 grade student

Muhammadaliyeva Ruxsora Murodaliyevna,

FerPI, Economics department, 3 grade student

Annotation: *In the rapidly evolving global digital landscape, Uzbekistan is making strides to harness the potential of technology to drive its socio-economic growth. Central to this transformation are the skilled IT specialists who are playing a pivotal role in shaping the*

nation's future. This article explores how these professionals serve as catalysts for Uzbekistan's digital revolution, bridging the gap between traditional industries and the tech-driven world of tomorrow. From driving innovation to building critical infrastructure, the contribution of Uzbekistan's IT talent is integral to the country's ambitious vision of a digital economy. Join us as we delve into the vital role these specialists are playing in this transformative journey.

Key words: *Digital era, IT specialist , e-commerce, information technologies, IT industry*

Introduction:

In alignment with Uzbekistan's ambitious *2030 Strategy*, announced by the President on September 11, 2023, the country is setting its sights on becoming a leading IT hub in the region. The strategy outlines several key objectives aimed at accelerating digital transformation and boosting the country's tech sector. These include increasing internet speeds by tenfold, exporting IT products valued at \$5 billion, expanding the number of IT Park residents by ten times, and raising the IT sector's contribution to GDP to 2.2%. In addition, the strategy envisions creating 100,000 new jobs within the sector, developing 1,000 multimedia programs, fostering stronger collaborations between manufacturing, higher education, and research organizations, as well as digitizing all medical institutions. Furthermore, there are plans to improve the technological literacy of the population and strengthen the overall digital infrastructure across various industries.

To achieve these ambitious goals, both the government and the private sector are taking coordinated yet complementary actions. Through strategic investments, policy reforms, and the nurturing of talent, Uzbekistan is positioning itself to become a regional leader in IT innovation and digital transformation, creating a foundation for sustained economic growth and societal development [1].

Research&Methodologies

Mathematical and statistical techniques, along with macroeconomic data, are employed to make comparisons with other countries and regions globally. Furthermore, conclusions are derived by synthesizing research and theories from various authors to summarize and contrast findings both internationally and within Uzbekistan.

Findings

IT specialists play a crucial role in the development of society and can have a significant impact on the increase in real GDP. Their influence stems from a variety of factors, including innovation, productivity improvements, and the growth of digital industries.

Below, I'll outline how IT specialists contribute to economic development, with statistical details and examples from around the world.

IT specialists are at the forefront of developing new technologies, from software to hardware, that can revolutionize industries. Innovations in areas such as artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, and data analytics create new business opportunities and streamline existing processes. This, in turn, boosts productivity and fosters economic growth. In the United States, the tech industry has contributed significantly to GDP growth. According to the *Bureau of Economic Analysis*, the "digital economy" contributed nearly 10% of U.S. GDP in 2020 [2]. A large part of this growth can be attributed to IT specialists, who create the technologies that enable businesses to function more efficiently and develop new products and services.

IT specialists help businesses adopt digital tools, automate processes, and improve supply chains. These changes lead to higher productivity and, ultimately, contribute to GDP growth. IT specialists are also crucial in sectors like healthcare, education, and manufacturing, where digital transformation is driving improvements in efficiency. In Estonia, a country known for its advanced digital government services, the digital economy accounts for around 6.5% of GDP, as reported by the *World Bank*. IT specialists have played a key role in creating digital platforms for public services, allowing the country to save time and resources [3]. Estonia's success in digital transformation has not only improved public services but also contributed to economic growth.

IT specialists directly contribute to the growth of digital industries, which in turn contributes to real GDP. For example, the tech industry's rapid expansion in countries like India, South Korea, and China has been a major driver of GDP growth. As more businesses and consumers move online, IT specialists help create the infrastructure that supports this transition. India's information technology sector is a prime example. According to *NASSCOM*, the Indian IT industry generated \$194 billion in revenue in 2021, accounting for approximately 8% of India's GDP [4]. The sector also provides millions of jobs, many of which are filled by skilled IT professionals. The growth of the Indian IT sector has led to increased productivity and contributed to India's overall economic development.

IT specialists enable the growth of e-commerce platforms, digital financial services, and other online marketplaces, which have become major drivers of economic activity. The increased availability of online platforms for buying and selling goods has led to greater market access for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and improved trade efficiency. China's booming e-commerce industry is a prime example of how IT specialists have driven GDP growth. Platforms like Alibaba and JD.com have transformed

retail and logistics. According to *Statista*, China's e-commerce market size reached approximately \$2.3 trillion in 2021, contributing heavily to both GDP growth and job creation [5].

IT specialists contribute to the financial sector by developing technologies such as blockchain, fintech, and digital banking, which increase the efficiency of financial transactions and enable greater financial inclusion. As access to financial services improves, businesses and consumers can engage in more productive economic activities. In the UK, the fintech sector has played an important role in driving economic growth. According to *UK Finance*, the UK fintech industry generated over £11 billion in revenue in 2020, with many IT specialists involved in creating and maintaining digital payment systems, lending platforms, and financial management tools [6]. This growth has supported job creation and increased GDP.

The *International Monetary Fund (IMF)* estimates that the global digital economy now contributes around 15.5% of global GDP, with significant growth in digital services, e-commerce, and tech-driven industries [7].

The *Information Technology and Innovation Foundation (ITIF)* reports that the U.S. tech sector directly contributed \$2 trillion to GDP in 2020 [8], with IT specialists playing a central role in this achievement.

In Brazil, the digital economy contributed approximately 6.8% to the country's GDP in 2021, with IT professionals involved in building infrastructure and promoting tech-driven industries [9], according to *OECD*.

The influence of IT specialists on society and real GDP growth is undeniable. They are central to technological innovation, productivity improvements, and the expansion of the digital economy. By developing new technologies, enhancing efficiencies, and creating new markets, IT specialists contribute directly to economic growth and the overall development of a country [10]. As economies continue to digitalize, the role of IT professionals will only become more crucial, driving future GDP increases and societal progress [11].

Table 1. The volume of rendered market communication and informatization services (in actual prices, billion soums)

Indicators	2020	2021	change %	2022	change %
programming and broadcasting services	650,9	696,7	107,0	833,1	119,6
telecommunication services	10 233,70	11 957,30	116,8	14 660,70	122,6
computer programming services, consulting and other related services	1 428,20	2 721,50	190,6	4 652,90	171,0
information services	708,7	1 373,60	193,8	2 516,00	183,2

Source: compiled by the authors [12]

As shown in Table 1, the value of IT services in monetary terms has been steadily increasing over time. Clearly, if greater attention is given to nurturing and supporting young, talented students in the field, the output from this sector is likely to grow exponentially. By investing in education and fostering innovation among the youth, Uzbekistan can further accelerate the expansion of its IT industry, driving both economic growth and technological advancement.

Table 2. Number of active organizations by types of economic activity "Information and Communication" (as of January 1, 2023, units).

Industries	2021	2022	change %	2023	change %
Release of computer games	136	130	95,6	156	120,0
Release of other software	315	352	111,7	425	120,7
Computer programming activities	896	1121	125,1	1618	144,3
Consulting services in the field of computer technology	387	461	119,1	536	116,3
Computer equipment management activities	198	243	122,7	290	119,3
Other activities in the field of information technology and computer systems	1 433	1 596	111,4	1 993	124,9
Data placement and processing services	510	628	123,1	704	112,1

Source: compiled by the authors [12]

As we can observe from Table 2, the release of computer games in the country has experienced some fluctuations over a short period. In contrast, software releases have shown consistent growth, reflecting the increasing demand for digital solutions. Other services related to the IT sector, such as digital platforms and cybersecurity, have also been expanding steadily.

It's important to highlight, however, that this industry's growth is highly dependent on factors like internet coverage and reliable electricity supply. The interdependence of these elements makes it clear that any disruptions in connectivity or power can have a significant impact on the overall productivity of the IT sector. For this reason, strengthening infrastructure, particularly in remote areas, is crucial for sustaining long-term growth and ensuring the resilience of the IT industry.

As the country focuses on expanding its digital capabilities, attention must also be paid to enhancing these foundational elements, ensuring a stable and supportive environment for IT services to thrive.

Conclusion:

The IT sector holds immense potential to become a driving force for Uzbekistan's overall economic development. With a young, dynamic, and rapidly growing labor force, the country is well-positioned to harness the benefits of digital transformation and technological innovation. The IT sector could serve as a catalyst for growth across all industries, from agriculture and tourism [13] to mining, by enabling greater efficiency, productivity, and access to global markets.

To fully unlock this potential, it is crucial that Uzbekistan implements a comprehensive strategy that includes targeted economic stimulation through both fiscal and monetary policies. Fiscal measures, such as tax reductions for IT companies, would incentivize growth and innovation within the sector, attracting more investment and fostering a supportive business environment [14]. Similarly, monetary policies that offer preferential loans to tech startups, along with easing exchange rates, can further stimulate expansion and global competitiveness.

By creating a favorable ecosystem for the IT sector [15], Uzbekistan can achieve significant economies of scale in the long run, where the benefits of technological advancements permeate throughout the economy, leading to sustained growth, job creation, and enhanced living standards. With the right policies and investments, the IT sector can not only drive economic growth but also position Uzbekistan as a regional leader in the digital economy.

References:

1. Presidential decree #158, strategy “Uzbekistan 2030”, 11th of September, 2023
2. Nicholson, J. R., Howells III, T. F., & Wasshausen, D. B. (2023). Measuring the US digital economy. *Advances in Business Statistics, Methods and Data Collection*, 105-124.
3. Kuosmanen, N., Seppäläinen, T. O., & Ylhäinen, I. (2022). *Greenhouse gas emissions of Finland's information economy sector: A supply chain perspective* (No. 122). ETLA Report.
4. Kumar, N. (2023). Unlocking India's Potential in Industrial Revolution 4.0: National Innovation System, Demography, and Inclusive Development. *Indian Public Policy Review*, 4(3), 67-87.
5. Li, Y., Xu, C., & Zhu, P. (2023). Analysis of the Development Environment and Trend of Cross-Border E-commerce in China. *Proceedings of Business and Economic Studies*, 6(6), 30-38.
6. Luu, L., Petratos, P. N., Nguyen, T., & Le, V. (2021). Financial technology (fintech). In *A Practical Guide to Financial Services* (pp. 143-171). Routledge.

7. Szeles, M. R., & Simionescu, M. (2020). Regional patterns and drivers of the EU digital economy. *Social Indicators Research*, 150(1), 95-119.
8. Ezell, S., & Dascoli, L. (2021). *How an Information Technology Agreement 3.0 Would Bolster Global Economic Growth and Opportunity*. Information Technology and Innovation Foundation.
9. Feijó, C., Lamônica, M. T., & Lima, S. D. S. (2022). Growth and stagnation in a dual economy: The case of Brazil. *PSL Quarterly Review*, 75(301), 119-138.
10. Akhunova, S. N., & Askarov, F. R. (2023). THE PROSPECTS FOR UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE IN THE DIGITAL ERA. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(16).
11. Butaboyev, M. T., & Askarov, F. R. (2023). THE INTERNET COVERAGE IN UZBEKISTAN SERVES AS A PRIMARY SOURCE OF INFORMATION FOR THE FOURTH INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION. *The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations*, 5(12), 06-16.
12. www.stat.uz
13. Akhunova, S., & Askarov, F. (2023). Perspectives for the Further Development of Smart Tourism in Uzbekistan.
14. Ahmadjonovich, U. A., & Rakhmatovich, A. F. (2023). UTILIZING DYNAMIC MODELS IN ANALYZING INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES IN REGIONS. *The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations*, 5(12), 29-35.
15. Askarov, F. R., & Numanov, J. O. (2023). NECESSITY OF INTEGRATING SPECIALISTS THROUGH A COMBINATION OF EDUCATION AND PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE IN THE WORKPLACE IN THE ERA OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 14), 746-756.

Full name	Farhod Raxmatovich Askarov
Academic title, position, workplace and country	FerPI, Economics department, assistant.
e-mail	farhod.asqarov@ferpi.uz
Title of the paper	IT SPECIALISTS AS CATALYSTS FOR

	UZBEKISTAN'S DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION
Key words	<i>Digital era, IT specialist , e-commerce, information technologies, IT industry</i>